

INTERESTING PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN LITERARY WORKS

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Abstract. *It is known that with the help of human thinking, there is more than what is seen with the eyes learns things. And in education based only on what we see, how much more than the student it is required to know as much as you have seen. This situation limits the student's knowledge, narrows it down. Simplifying education is always true to educational principles unfortunately, he noticed that he wouldn't come too late. The educational process is too much relief is like giving a big child to chew food.*

Keywords: *literature, education, effective, work analysis, teaching process, maturity, theory.*

Organization of primary school classes, the student as a moral person the following principles of education are leading for formation: - lesson plan change. According to this, the lessons are in the traditional way, that is, the organizational part, homework asking and strengthening it, new lesson statement and strengthening it, giving homework is not implemented in this way. The lesson is based on a new work presented in the program while working, relying on the students' previous knowledge and life experiences asking controversial questions and ensuring students' independent work based on relevance of teaching to life. Life lessons in traditional education it is the teacher's duty to ensure the relevance. The student's moral in lessons aimed at perfection, the concept of science based on life events and they themselves absorb its laws, they return from theory to life giving tasks to the student for independent activity. Literary education in this principle of organization, asking for homework can be done in groups or in groups is carried out by execution in the form Pupils to master a new subject achieves tasks independently, i.e., by working hard.

Independent works are presented creatively or semi-creatively. A short one that takes 3-4 minutes term independent work also activates students; - individualization of education. Individualization of the lesson process in the study of literary examples is a gap in the acquisition of knowledge to prevent it from happening, as much as possible with each of the students consists of working. When working with each student individually, his/her individual characteristics, uniqueness in knowledge acquisition, memory, level of acquisition, character and interests must be taken into account.

Arousing interest in fiction in primary school students expressed in rare examples of human intelligence broader conditions for learning knowledge and life experiences is created. Arousing students' interest in fiction reading serves as the main tool [1].

Teachers always emphasize the importance of artistic examples to students. Reading is the best exercise, they say. As a result of students' interest in works of art and feeling the need to study. Without doing this, the value of reading a book cannot be appreciated. First of all, by improving children's speech, art works expand their vocabulary. Students who are familiar with artistic examples create memories and focus on one area. In addition, it improves children's literacy and metaphorical thinking. Students will understand the basic concept of artistic creation and their

public speaking skills. As a result, they develop analytical thinking successfully. Constant reading of examples of fiction helps to form children's moral character, outlook, intelligence and cognitive functions. Readers will learn about the value of caring for the environment through the characters who serve as the heroes of the work, and become aware of the subtleties of interpersonal relationships. Students need more information when they enter school every day. For this reason, teachers should gradually extend the reading time, cooperate closely with parents, and offer literary works to read according to the age of the students. Teachers must sincerely believe that reading art will fill their children with a deep sense of happiness. A teacher can make students interested in this work by explaining their feelings about the same work chosen as an alternative. Teachers and parents should continue to encourage students to read, even if they can read a particular book or story independently.

Primary-school textbooks introduce pupils to a wide range of narrative texts, most of them belonging to the epic genre, which is more accessible to them, from various literary species - fairy tales, stories, legends, ballads, sketches, anecdotes, fables, short stories, and novels. Those literary works tell the lives of children and adults, small creatures, moments from past history, aspects of personalities' lives, etc. The narrative texts intended for the study of primary-school pupils have well-built topics and logical deployment of actions, which gives the teacher the opportunity to guide pupils, by using their intuition, towards the understanding of the artistic message.

Readers should be encouraged to read books with great illustrations and pictures. Even knowing the identity of the illustrator who created the covers for these books would be helpful for students. A work of art should be given tasks that require students to create images based on their own work or portray the characters of the work. Every student needs his favorite novels. These books primarily affect their field of interest and help them grow productively. For this, parents and teachers should set a good example for children by having a positive attitude towards books. Students have characteristics common to three major groups of fiction readers. a) A set of methods used in the educational process. Elementary school teachers use these methods to teach reading. For this process to be successful, students must interact with literary examples to develop as readers, become literate readers, and develop an ongoing interest in literary examples; b) the principles defining the scope of study formed by students represent the unity of the theory.

In primary education, learning to read is performed in two stages: the first stage corresponds to the actual literacy (1st grade) when pupils learn the reading mechanism operations and begin to form the ability to sense and understand the meaning of texts they read; The second stage corresponds to practicing and achieving qualitative reading (IInd to IVth grade) when pupils learn the correct reading - clear speak without omissions or additions of sounds, inversions of syllables or words; fluent reading - fluent rhythm, fluent reading awareness - pupils understand the purpose of their reading, engaging thinking operations and affective processes; expressive reading - the ability of pupils to suggest, by intonation, stress, rhythm, and pauses, ideas and feelings expressed in text [2].

By reading literary texts, pupils develop their ability to discover important contents and different forms of reality, that authors describe through a variety of means of expression, to pair them with previous information and thus broaden their knowledge, from concrete to abstract facts, from intuition to fantasy, and acquire useful tools to satisfy their desire to understand the surrounding reality. The ways in which teachers lead their pupils to understand the message of a literary text depend on the thematic content of the respective text, as well as the literary genre and

species it belongs to. The mixture of genres in a literary work increases pupils' responsiveness. Thus, if at their early contact with literature, they are drawn to epic works (by discovering the moments of action: exposition, plot, progress, climax and denouement - that the teacher will address in detail and carefully), along the way, as they develop their abilities to perceive literary texts, pupils will become sensitive to poetic expressiveness, they will identify "beautiful expressions" (figures of speech) in poetry and begin to understand their role in highlighting the poetic ideas and feelings expressed in text. The literary characters become symbols of good and evil that pupils compare and identify themselves, they meet creatures endowed with human features and patterns of social behaviour, which they start to imitate, if positive, or reject if negative.

In first (or most important) school, pupils will be exposed to poetic texts on different topics: pastels, country-loving poems, emotional poems, songs, beautiful writing texts, etc. If in the IInd grade, the study of poems mainly aims at the correct, (able to easily and correctly speak or write a language) and (communicating a lot of thought or emotion) reading, and at educating pupils' sensitivity, starting with the IIIrd grade, the content of the text will be carefully studied more deeply, while explaining pupils the beautiful expressions, taking account of gained knowledge, and doing exercises using expressions in new contexts, this way positively influencing the pupils' language. The poems are carefully studied from the point of view of versification, but without naming the ideas of rhythm or rhyme, and leading the pupils to the (gut feeling or deep-down opinion) of these ideas of book-related explanation (of why something works or happens the way it does). So, one can figure out the number of syllables in a line, or identify almost the same endings of lines (rhyme), or the accents and successions at equal periods of time (or space) (rhythm). This way, pupils will find other sources of musicality in the poetic text, which will allow them to better understand the poetic message.

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